

Speculation on Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and Antisymmetry

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Spin $\frac{1}{2}$, which follows from Dirac's linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation, is associated with a fermion which in turn is linked to an antisymmetric spin wavefunction under the permutation of particles if other quantum numbers are the same, e.g. energy etc.

We argue that the Klein-Gordon equation with a rest mass m_0 implies a rest frame in which one may observe rotations. If one wishes to linearize E , one may write: $E = \pm \sqrt{p \cdot p + m_0^2 c^2}$ ($c=1$). Here $p \cdot p$ is rotationally invariant, but E and p_x, p_y and p_z are treated in a different manner even though E and (p_x, p_y, p_z) appear equally as vector entries of a 4-vector. As a result, one may attempt to linearize the Klein-Gordon equation $-E^2 + p^2 = -m_0^2 c^4$ to have E and p_x, p_y, p_z appear on the same footing. This, however, cannot be done using numbers, but requires 4x4 matrices containing 2x2 Pauli matrices as shown by Dirac. We consider the simpler case here of the Pauli 2x2 matrices such that: $A = s_x p(x) + s_y p(y) + s_z p(z)$ and $AA = -E^2 + p \cdot p$. The Pauli matrices are 2x2 and ensure that there is orthogonality among $p(x), p(y), p(z)$ so no cross terms appear in AA .

The 2x2 Pauli matrices, however, are linked with more than orthogonality of $p(x), p(y), p(z)$. Given that $s_x s_x = s_y s_y = s_z s_z = 1$, they carry the same feature of the sqrt function, namely that -1 or 1 squared yields 1. In this case, if one considers the two eigenvectors of s_z , namely (1,0) and (0,1), the second has an eigenvalue of -1. One must operate twice with s_z i.e. $s_z s_z$ in order to restore 1. Thus s_z is a kind of square root rotation.

So far, there has been no mention of antisymmetry which requires at least two particles. If one considers $W(\text{spin}) = |+\rangle|-\rangle + a|-\rangle|+\rangle$, where $|+\rangle = (1,0)$ and $|-\rangle = (0,1)$, (where a could be +1 or -1), one may ask: Is there a condition on an operator which permutes the first particle and second? Here $|n\rangle|m\rangle$ applies to the first particle in state n and the second in m . We consider the operator $s_z(1) s_z(2)$, where 1 and 2 denote particles 1 and 2, acting on $W(\text{spin})$. For a single particle, s_z acting on $|-\rangle$ returns a -1 eigenvalue, and so for a mixed $|+\rangle|-\rangle$, an eigenvalue of -1 is also returned. We argue that this represents a physical situation and so the permutation operator should also return the same physical state because Permutation operator * Permutation operator = 1. Thus, we suggest that a permutation should have the same effect as $s_z(1)s_z(2)$. This suggests that $a = -1$ i.e. one has $|+\rangle|-\rangle - |-\rangle|+\rangle$ in order that the permutation operator have the same effect as $s_z(1)s_z(2)$.

$$E = \pm \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2 c^2} \quad (c=1)$$

Before relativity, one used Newton's equation which link a free particle energy and momentum through: $E = p \cdot p / 2m_0$. With special relativity, however, one has a four vector:

(p_x, p_y, p_z, E) with a metric which applies a -1 to the 4th component and:

$$-E^2 + p^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1)) \quad (c=1)$$

((1)) has a rest mass m_0 suggesting a rest frame which may be used to observe rotations of the vector p . If $m_0=0$, ((1)) represents a photon, but there is no longer a rest frame and it seems one cannot observe physically the rotations of p from an intrinsic particle based frame. Thus spin (rotation) for a photon is associated with the perpendicularity of the B field and E field (but also a physical rotation). In particular, the spin matrix is ϵ_{ijk} (Levi Civita symbol) which appears in the cross product:

$$(\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B})_i = \epsilon_{ijk} E_j B_k \quad \text{where } E_i \text{ is the electric field and } B_i \text{ the magnetic } ((2))$$

By using m_0 , we focus on a particle with rest mass and consider the idea of rotation relative to a fixed intrinsic rest frame, i.e. there could be an inherent rotational property of such a particle.

$$\text{Mathematically, one may write: } E = \pm \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2} \quad (c=1) \quad ((3)).$$

If energy is taken to be positive, one would use $+$. A possible issue with the form ((3)) is that E appears in a linear form, but $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ do not. This contradicts the symmetry between E and $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ in the 4-vector:

$$(p(x), p(y), p(z), E) \quad ((4))$$

As a result, Dirac wrote a linear expression in E , $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ using generalized numbers. When this generalized number is multiplied by its complex conjugate it returns the Klein-Gordon expression $-E^2 + p^2 = -m_0^2$. It was already known that E and p vector may be obtained by using operators $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-\text{grad}$. Thus a generalized number would also serve as an operator. Dirac found 4x4 matrices based on the 2x2 Pauli matrices.

For simplicity, we consider here $p \cdot p$ and only the Pauli matrices. Then:

$$A = s_x p(x) + s_y p(y) + s_z p(z) \quad ((5)) \text{ such that } A^2 = -E^2 + p \cdot p$$

$$\text{This implies that: } s_x^2 = s_y^2 = s_z^2 = 1 \text{ and } s_x s_y + s_y s_x = s_x s_z + s_z s_x = s_y s_z + s_z s_y = 0 \quad ((6))$$

The Pauli matrices satisfy ((6)) and are linked with a kind of rotation, but this should be examined in more detail. Consider s_z :

$$s_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((7))$$

s_z has two eigenfunctions $(1,0)$ with eigenvalue 1 and $(0,1)$ with eigenvalue -1. Thus for $(0,1)$ one requires s_z^2 to return the vector $(0,1)$ to itself (i.e. a full rotation). Thus the Pauli matrices do not only ensure the orthogonality of $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ (through the anticommutation of ((6))), but also carry the square root property of ((3)) i.e. $\sqrt{1} = \pm 1$. s_z is like a square root operator. One may obtain -1 because a second operation of s_z on $(0,1)$ yields $(-1)(-1)$.

We suggest that:

$S_z(0,1) = -1(0,1)$ represents a physically allowed operation on the state $(0,1)$ ((8))

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The above discussion only pertains to a single particle with rest mass which satisfies the Klein-Gordon equation, which seemingly applies to all particles and even photons. How is the Pauli matrix result associated with an antisymmetric wavefunction under the permutation of two particles? As noted, one needs at least two particles in order to permute them. We consider the mixed form:

$$W(\text{spin}) = |+\rangle|-\rangle + a|-\rangle|+\rangle \quad \text{where } a = +1 \text{ or } -1 \quad \text{and } |+\rangle = (1,0) \text{ and } |-\rangle = (0,1) \quad ((9))$$

The first $|+\rangle$ represents particle 1 and the second particle 2. We ask: Can one determine whether a is $+1$ or -1 ? We argue that one can. The permutation operator P acting twice on $W(\text{spin})$ returns the wavefunction $W(\text{spin})$. $W(\text{spin})$, however, is a spin wavefunction. Its changes must correspond to actions of the generator s_z , we argue. These are the physically allowed changes to such a spin wavefunction based on the generator s_z . Thus

(A) the action of the permutation operator cannot be considered independent of the action of the spin operator s_z .

The spin operator $s_z(1)s_z(2)$ corresponds to a kind of half rotation (seen by its action on $|-\rangle$). When acting twice, it returns the eigenvalue $+1$. Thus $s_z(1)s_z(2)s_z(1)s_z(2)$ is identical to Permutation Permutation. Furthermore:

$$\text{Permutation } W(\text{spin}) = s_z(1)s_z(2) W(\text{spin}) \quad ((10))$$

$s_z(1)s_z(2)$ acting on a mixed $|+\rangle|-\rangle$ pair returns a -1 . The permutation operator must also return a -1 eigenvalue. This implies that a in ((9)) should be -1 so that the wavefunction is antisymmetric, i.e. returns an eigenvalue of -1 . This has important consequences because it means each particle must have a different spin even if their p and E are the same. This is the Pauli exclusion principle for fermions.

Does this mean that all particles associated with the Klein-Gordon equation have spin $\frac{1}{2}$, i.e. are associated with Pauli matrices and are fermions. The answer is no. A photon satisfies the Klein-Gordon equation with $m_0=0$, but ((5)) does not apply to it because there is no rest mass frame. The spin of a photon is 1 from $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ i.e. ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi-Civita symbol). One may have a spin 0 object as well which satisfies the Klein-Gordon equation. Thus ((5)) seems to be a special case, albeit an important one because it describes electrons and nucleons among other particles.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may linearize the Klein-Gordon equation $-\mathbf{E}\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} = -m_0m_0$, but this is associated with rotations which may be measured in a rest frame (implied by m_0).

One cannot use this linearization approach for photons which have $m_0=0$. Linearizing using generalized numbers, Dirac found these were 4×4 matrices linked to 2×2 Pauli matrices. We consider the simpler case of 2×2 Pauli matrices which allow for:

$p(x)s_x + p(y)s_y + p(z)s_z = A$ to yield $AA = -EE + p \cdot p$.

The 2×2 Pauli matrices ensure the orthogonality of $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$, i.e. eliminate any cross terms such as $p(x)p(y)$ in AA . They, however, carry the important feature of a square root, namely that $+1$ or -1 squared equals 1. s_z has two eigenvectors $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ with eigenvalues $+1$, -1 . The latter shows that s_z , a kind of rotation generation operator, must be applied twice to $(0,1)$ to return it to $+1$ $(0,1)$. We consider this an important physical result. We suggest this result is associated with the symmetry of the spin wavefunction of a two particle system.

If one considers $|+\rangle|-\rangle + a|-\rangle|+\rangle$ with $a=+1$ or -1 , we suggest that a permutation operator P which interchanges the two particles must have the same effect as the spin operator $s_z(1)s_z(2)$, which is the generator which acts in this spin space. In other words, a permutation in spin space cannot achieve different results from the $s_z(1)s_z(2)$ generator. When both the permutation operator and $s_z(1)s_z(2)$ are applied twice, both return the state to its original, but with $|-\rangle$ present, s_z yields a -1 eigenvalue. Thus a Permutation on $W(\text{spin})$ must also yield a -1 eigenvalue. This ensures that $a=-1$, i.e. one has an antisymmetric spin wavefunction which pertains to fermions and does not allow for both particles to be in the same spin eigenstate (if other quantum numbers are the same.)